

Effects of Different Synthesis Methods on the Photo Electrochemical Performance of CdS Nanoparticles

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Abstract

In the present study, nanoparticles (NPs) of CdS were synthesized using three different approaches viz. solvothermal (CdS-s), hydrothermal (CdS-h) and chemical reduction (CdS-c) methods for analyzing the effects of these synthesis procedures on the electrocatalytic as well as photocatalytic activity of CdS NPs. The Optical properties of as prepared CdS NPs were characterized using UV-Visible spectroscopy and Photoluminescence spectroscopy. The optical energy gap calculated from Tauc's relation using Kubelka-Munk function depicted a decrease in energy gap from CdS-s to CdS-c. This may be due to the formation of trap states in between HOMO and LUMO levels of CdS-c NPs. Photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy also depicted quenching in emission peaks of CdS-c and CdS-h NPs, attributed to the inclusions of trap states. Structural characterization using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) revealed the hexagonal structure of as synthesized CdS NPs. The size of CdS-c NPs calculated from Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) image using imageJ software came out to be 7.07 ± 0.66 nm. The enhanced electrocatalytic activity of CdS-c NP catalysts was investigated by performing electrochemical techniques: Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS). The CdS-c NPs exhibited highest photocurrent density of ~ 1.57 mA/cm² at 1.5 V (vs SHE) and lowest charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of 13 Ω .

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Band Gap, photocatalysts, electrocatalysts, EIS, Cyclic Voltammetry.

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Introduction

The search for a sustainable, reliable and environment friendly energy source has made green hydrogen production an attractive area of research owing to its high calorific value, non-toxicity and light weight (Hamdani et al. 2021, Ke et al. 2022). Photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting is a process in which solar energy is converted into chemical energy to produce hydrogen via an external bias applied to a photovoltaic material-based electrode immersed in an electrolyte solution. This process makes use of water splitting reaction to produce hydrogen given by,

In thermodynamics, the spontaneity of an electrochemical reaction is determined by Gibbs free energy. The Gibbs free energy (ΔG) for water splitting depends primarily on the electrolyzer's temperature, pressure, and pH of the electrolyte solution. Under standard conditions (298 K and pH = 0), the thermodynamic Gibbs free energy required for water splitting is ~237.2 kJ/mol which corresponds to the theoretical limit of 1.23 V. Splitting of water to produce hydrogen is therefore an uphill reaction as it requires a higher enthalpy of 237 kJ/mol. (Yasin et al. 2022)

The major factor that determines the performance of a PEC cell is the choice of electrode material. The selection of material is done by taking following points into consideration: i) it must have a band gap greater than 1.23 eV; ii) band edges should be suitable for water redox reactions; iii) it should have large diffusion length so that charges may not recombine quickly (Huang et al. 2015). Semiconductors having band gap in the visible range are the most efficient photocatalysts as they utilize major part of the solar spectrum. Transition metal chalcogenides like metal sulphides, oxides etc. are promising materials because of the tunable band gaps and high catalytic activity (Hisatomi et al. 2014).

Cadmium sulphide (CdS) is a II-VI transition metal chalcogenide which offers ample applications in optoelectronics, photocatalysis, solar cells etc. (Rahane et al. 2021, Wang et al. 2015, Zhu et al. 2014). It is an n-type semiconductor having direct band gap of 2.42 eV which lies in the visible range of solar spectrum (Hullavarad et al. 2008). Its band edges are consistent with water oxidation and reduction reactions as depicted in figure 1, which makes it an efficient

material for PEC water splitting (Nasir et al. 2020). The performance of CdS in PEC water splitting however is greatly affected by the morphological properties, size, shape and crystallinity of the nanoparticles. The synthesis technique used for CdS significantly influences these characteristics (Peng 2003). For example, its optical and electronic properties are influenced by the size of the nanoparticles. Moreover, the shape of the nanoparticles impacts the surface area and active sites of the material influencing its photoelectrochemical properties. Furthermore, the crystallinity affects charge carrier mobility and recombination rates which impacts the efficiency of PEC cells (Pederson 2006, Streetman & Banerjee 2006).

Now, as the synthesis methods play a crucial role to determine the electrochemical properties of CdS, an extensive investigation is required to study the effects of various techniques to synthesize CdS. Out of the different available synthesis methods, three popular techniques are: solvothermal method, hydrothermal method and chemical reduction. These methods offer different advantages and challenges which affect the characteristics of the synthesized nanoparticles further influencing the photocatalytic properties of the synthesized material.

In this study, we endeavor to synthesize CdS NPs by the above listed approaches and characterize them using optical, structural and electrochemical techniques to unveil the role of synthesis procedures on the PEC performance of CdS. The photoelectrochemical measurements were carried out by fabricating photoelectrodes of as synthesized samples on nickel foam which is a novel study as to best of our knowledge.

Figure 1: Illustration showing band edge positions of CdS w.r.t redox potential of water

1. Experimental Details

1.1. Chemicals

Chemicals like Cadmium acetate dihydrate ($\text{Cd}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Thiourea (NH_2CSNH_2), Ethanol and Ethylenediamine ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$) were purchased from Rankem Pvt. Ltd. All the chemicals were used as procured without further purification. Nickel foam of 110 ppi was purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

1.2. Synthesis of CdS by Solvothermal method.

In order to synthesize pure CdS NPs, 0.533 g (0.05 M) of ($\text{Cd}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was mixed in 40 mL of EDA ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$) and stirred the resultant solution. Thereafter, 0.480 g (0.05 M) of (NH_2CSNH_2) was added slowly into the obtained solution under vigorous stirring. The resultant solution was then kept for further stirring until the solution was turned to light yellow. The yellow solution was transferred to a 50 mL of Teflon lined autoclave and heated at 120°C for 12 h. The autoclave was then cooled to room temperature. The obtained precipitates were washed with deionized water and ethanol using centrifugation. The obtained yellow solid material was thus dried at 60°C for 24 hours (Kumar and Ojha, 2016)

1.3. Synthesis of CdS by Hydrothermal method.

The similar procedure as solvothermal process was followed for the hydrothermal synthesis. The only difference is that here deionized water (DI) is used as solvent instead of EDA. An orange color CdS-h NPs were obtained.

1.4. Synthesis of CdS by chemical reduction.

For synthesis of CdS nanoparticles using chemical reduction, 0.05M thiourea was mixed to 0.007M cadmium acetate solution under stirring. After this, few drops of liquid ammonia were added to the above mixture under stirring to bring the pH of solution to 11. This changed the colour of the solution to orange. In the next step, the mixture was allowed to heat at 80°C until the formation of precipitates. This was followed by centrifugation to collect the solid precipitate followed by drying in an oven at 60°C for 24 hours. Again, the colour of obtained product was light orange in colour (Xu et al. 2016).

1.5. Preparation of Electrodes

In order to prepare the electrodes for Photoelectrochemical catalytic activity, powder samples of as synthesized CdS NPs were dispersed in ethanol and a slurry was prepared using pestle and

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mortar. A small amount of slurry was then drop casted on nickel foam and it was left to dry. Afterwards, the electrodes were used for photoelectrochemical measurements. A schematic showing the synthesis of CdS NPs, preparation of electrodes and their photoelectrochemical measurements is illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic of preparation of electrodes and the set up showing PEC cell and electrochemical workstation.

2. Characterization Techniques

The crystallography of as synthesized samples was characterized using Bruker X-ray diffractometer using Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda=1.54\text{\AA}$) at a scan speed of $1^\circ/\text{min}$ in the 2θ range of 20° to 80° . FTIR spectra was recorded using MB3000 spectrophotometer. The surface morphology was investigated using JEOL SEM by depositing palladium coating on samples and the elemental mapping is obtained by EDX using OXFORD instrument equipped with SEM. The high resolution TEM images of nanoparticles were obtained using JEOL JEM-F200 at an accelerating voltage of 200kV. The size distribution and average size of particles was calculated using imageJ software. The UV-Vis spectra were recorded using SHIMADZU UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer (UV-3600i Plus) in the wavelength range 200 to 1000 nm to study the diffuse reflectance spectra (DRS) using the integrating sphere attachment featuring 3-D detectors for

high sensitivity measurement of solid samples. The PL spectra was obtained using SHIMADZU RF-530 spectrophotometer equipped with 150 W Xenon lamp at an excitation wavelength of 310 nm. The electrochemical study was performed using AUTOLAB workstation (AUT86140) with NOVA 1.10.1.9 software using nickel foam modified electrodes.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Structural Analysis

3.1.1. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

In order to investigate the structure and crystallography, as synthesized CdS samples were subjected to XRD. As analyzed from the XRD patterns (figure 3), six main diffraction peaks correspond to (002), (100), (101), (110), (103), (112) planes as per JCPDS card (File No. 41-1049) are observed (Holder & Schaak 2019, Thakur et al. 2020). These planes attribute to the hexagonal phase geometry of prepared CdS samples.

Qualitatively, the broadening of peaks in XRD pattern of CdS-c (curve a) indicates the formation of smallest sized nanoparticles. The crystallite size of prepared CdS NPs was also calculated using Scherrer's formula $D = K\lambda/\beta\cos\theta$; where $K=0.94$ is crystal shape constant, $\lambda=1.54\text{\AA}$, θ is Bragg's diffraction angle (in radians) and β is FWHM (in radians). The position of peak and its FWHM was calculated by fitting the measured peak. The obtained values of crystallite size for all three CdS samples is tabulated in Table 1. The crystallite size is found to be smallest (~8nm) for CdS-c NPs. Also, strain generated in the lattice structure during synthesis of NPs is determined using the relation $\epsilon = \beta/4\tan\theta$ and dislocation density by $\delta = 1/D^2$, as tabulated in Table 1. It is observed that as size decreases, the strain in the lattice structure increases because of the increase in surface atoms. The dislocation density is found to be higher for CdS-c and CdS-h NPs. This clearly corresponds to the fact that smaller size of particles led to imperfections and defects in the crystal structure (Bindu & Thomas 2014, Bykkam et al. 2015, Tang et al. 2005).

Figure 3: XRD pattern of CdS nanoparticles prepared via different methods and their JCPDS file.

Table 1: The crystallite size, micro strain and dislocation density of CdS nanoparticles prepared via different methods.

Sample	Average Crystallite size (nm)	Micro strain ($\times 10^{-3}$)	Dislocation density ($\times 10^{-3}$) (nm ⁻²)
CdS-c	8	17.12	23.7
CdS-h	12	9.2	8.2
CdS-s	14	7.5	5.1

3.1.2 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR spectra provide useful information about the structure (vibrational modes) and functional groups attached to the material. Figure 4 shows the FTIR spectra of CdS NPs synthesized by different methods shown by curves a, b and c. The strong band at 3350-3500 cm⁻¹ corresponds to O-H stretching of water. The presence of peak at ~1000 cm⁻¹ may attribute to the stretching peaks of solvents used, N-H bond of EDA and NH₃ in CdS-s and CdS-c, respectively. The almost similar spectra for CdS-h and CdS-s (curves b and c) indicate similar structure for the two as a consequence of similar synthesis conditions, except one additional peak which may due

to the solvent effect. The common peak in all three samples appear in the fingerprint region at around 600 cm^{-1} . This corresponds to the characteristic peak of metal-sulphur (Cd-S) bond. The highest intensity for this peak is observed for CdS-c (curve a) which reflects the growth of smaller CdS-c NPs among as synthesized CdS NPs (Kumar et al. 2017, Tripathi et al. 2008).

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of CdS nanoparticles synthesized by different methods.

3.2 Morphological Analysis

3.2.1 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology of CdS samples was investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Figures 5 a,b and c represent the SEM images for CdS NPs prepared using three different methods. Their Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectra (EDX) were also recorded to analyze the corresponding elemental composition of samples (as shown in figures 5 d,e and f). These spectra confirm that all three samples are composed of Cd and S atoms only. The SEM image shown in figure 5a for CdS-c NPs clearly depicts the irregular morphology of surface with relatively high surface roughness due to collection of smaller sized particles. For CdS-h (figure 5b), there observed existence of many bigger sized particles with some tiny alterations on the surface. However, particles on the surface of CdS-s can be seen much agglomerated (figure 5c), resulting in flakes like arrangement of particles on the surface of CdS-s NPs. The high surface energy of nanomaterials is usually responsible for agglomeration. Because of the less polarity of EDA (used as solvent in CdS-s synthesis) in comparison to DI, the particles in CdS-s NPs appear to be

much agglomerated. Further, the elemental composition of all the CdS samples is given in the EDX spectra (figures 5(d)-(f)). The peaks in each of the EDX spectrum correspond to the presence of Cadmium (Cd) and Sulphur (S) atoms only and there is no evidence of presence of other impurities. The stoichiometry ratios of Cd to S atoms is found almost similar in all three samples.

Figure 5: SEM images (a-c); and EDX spectra (d-f) of CdS nanoparticles prepared via different methods.

3.2.2 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

The morphology of CdS nanoparticles so synthesized was investigated using TEM images. The average size of particles was calculated using ImageJ software by measuring diameter of about 50 nanoparticles as tabulated in Table 2. The particle size distribution plots are shown in figures 6 (D-F). The spherical particles observed in case of CdS-c (figure 6A) appear much densely distributed due to their smaller size (~7nm). This size reduction is a consequence of basic pH which is achieved by the addition of ammonia solution during the CdS-c synthesis. CdS-h NPs (figure 6B) on the other hand are less agglomerated due to their relatively bigger size because of the absence of any reducing agent and much polar solvent DI which prevents agglomeration. The

CdS-s NPs synthesized in the presence of EDA as a reducing agent, appear to be hexagonal in shape and much closely arranged/packed. This close packing may be due to lower polarity of EDA as compared to water, leading to slower ionization and deposition (Kumar et al. 2017). The interplanar spacing, $d=0.38$ nm and 0.41 nm corresponds to the (100) plane of CdS as evaluated from the imageJ software. Thus, confirms the formation of hexagonal structure of CdS in agreement with the XRD pattern.

Figure 6: TEM images and particle size distribution plots of (a) CdS-c; (b) CdS-h; (c) CdS-s samples.

Table 2: Average size of particles as calculated from TEM images.

Sample	Average Size (nm)
CdS-c	7.07 ± 0.66
CdS-h	11.00 ± 1.50
CdS-s	12.04 ± 2.79

3.3 Optical Study

3.3.1 UV-Visible Spectroscopy

The UV-Visible absorption spectra (converted from the reflectance spectra) of as synthesized powder samples (shown in figure 7) was recorded to determine the optical energy gap (E_g) using the Kubelka-Munk theory. The Kubelka-Munk theory holds for a particle size that is comparable or smaller than the wavelength of incident light. The powder samples were filled in a cylindrical cavity upto a small thickness of 1-3 mm. When the thickness of sample is small enough, it has no influence on the reflectance (Abdullahi et al. 2016).

Hence, the Kubelka-Munk equation at any wavelength can be written as

$$K/S = (1-R_\infty)^2 / 2R_\infty \equiv F(R_\infty) \dots\dots(1)$$

where S and K are scattering and absorption coefficients, R_∞ is the diffuse reflectance and $F(R_\infty)$ is called the Kubelka-Munk function.

As we know that, the Tauc's relation for a direct band gap material relating E_g and absorption coefficient (α) is given by the expression

$$\alpha hv = A (hv - E_g)^n \dots\dots(2)$$

where $n=1/2$ for direct band gap materials and A is the proportionality constant.

When the incident radiation scatters in a perfectly diffuse manner, the absorption coefficient K (in eq. 1) becomes equal to 2α . In this case, considering the scattering coefficient S as constant with respect to wavelength, the Kubelka-munk function is proportional to the absorption coefficient α (from eq. 1), therefore we obtain the relation:

$$(F(R_\infty) hv)^2 = A (hv - E_g) \dots\dots(3)$$

The optical energy gap (E_g) of the samples were calculated from the Tauc's relation given in equation (3). The $(F(R_\infty) hv)^2$ vs hv graphs were plotted for all three samples. In the graphs, a straight line is fitted for the straight segment with $R^2=0.99$. The extrapolation of this straight line to the x-axis gives the band gap values.

The obtained values of optical energy gap are given in Table 3. The shifting of energy gap to lower values for CdS-h and CdS-c indicates the presence of defects/trap states which may be created due to sulphur vacancies leading to incorporation of trapping levels within the HOMO

and LUMO levels. (He et al. 2003, Khatter & Chauhan 2020, Rao et al. 2011). This is in support with high strain and dislocation density evaluated from XRD pattern for CdS-c NPs.

Figure 7: (A) UV-Visible absorption spectra (converted from reflectance spectra) for CdS nanoparticles prepared using different methods. (B) Linear fitting of Tauc's plot for optical energy gap determination.

Table 3: Optical energy gap for CdS nanoparticles prepared via different methods.

Sample	Band Gap (eV)
CdS-s	2.35 ± 0.08
CdS-h	2.27 ± 0.06
CdS-c	2.163 ± 0.025

3.3.2 Photoluminescence (PL) Spectroscopy

The PL spectra for three CdS samples is shown in Figure 8. A significant change in PL spectrum of the three samples has been observed. It is a direct consequence of the change in electronic structure of the material owing to the process by which it has been synthesized. This may be due to the injection of defects and lattice strain generated during different synthesis process. The emission peaks obtained at ~550nm for CdS-s and at 565 nm for CdS-c and CdS-h samples correspond to band edge transitions. The significant high intensity emission peak at ~550nm for CdS-s sample corresponds to the optical band gap energy of 2.25 eV. Whereas for CdS-c and CdS-h samples, the emission band is broader and red shifted which may be due to wider size

distribution of particles and decrease in band gap energies, as demonstrated through UV-Vis absorption spectrum also. The high intensity emission peak in CdS-s signifies faster rate of recombination of charge carriers due to absence of any trap/metastable states between HOMO and LUMO levels whereas in case of CdS-c and CdS-h, pronounced quenching of PL peak is observed. The lesser intensity of emission peak for CdS-c and CdS-h corresponds to the existence of trapping states between HOMO and LUMO levels, which leads to non-radiative recombination and thus promotes efficient separation of charge carriers. Thus, CdS-c and CdS-h can be more potential candidates for photoelectrochemical application which is further studied in the electrochemical measurements (Gupta & Chauhan 2021, Roduner 2006, Tang et al. 2015, Thambidurai et al. 2010).

Figure 8: PL spectra for CdS nanoparticles prepared using different methods.

4. Electrochemical Study

The electrochemical measurements were performed using a three-electrode arrangement system consisting of working electrode (CdS NPs modified Ni foam), reference electrode (Ag/AgCl) and counter electrode (Pt wire) in 1M Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) electrolyte solution as shown in the schematic drawn for the set up used for measurements (figure 9). In order to study the photo electrochemical activity of prepared CdS NPs, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) and Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) scans were performed. The photocurrent density was also measured under light (ordinary tungsten filament lamp of 200W) in CV scans.

Figure 9: Illustration showing the three electrodes arrangement set up for carrying the electrochemical measurements

4.1 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

From the EIS data, we plotted the Nyquist plot between the real (Z') and imaginary ($-Z''$) part of impedance taken on x-axis and y-axis, respectively shown in Figure 10. It was operated in the frequency range 0.01 to 10^5 Hz by an applied a.c signal of 10mV. This plot gives the crucial information about the electrode-electrolyte interface kinematics. Usually, EIS plot includes a semicircle in the higher frequency region which intercept at x-axis and followed by a vertical steep rising line parallel to imaginary axis of impedance in the lower frequency region. The first intercept in the higher frequency region is attributed to series resistance (R_s) i.e. the contact resistance between electrode material and substrate. The second intercept of low frequency tail (as shown in inset of figure 10) determines charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and nearly vertical lines in low frequency region indicate the formation of electrical double layer at the electrode-electrolyte interface (Iesalniaks et al. 2024). For the EIS plot observed in figure 10, semicircle is not observed which may appear at much higher frequency. From the inclination of straight line in case of CdS-c more towards the y-axis attributes to its excellent capacitive behavior. The tail of the linear portion intersects the x-axis at $\sim 13 \Omega$ (shown in inset) corresponds to smaller charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) for CdS-c NPs in comparison to CdS-h and CdS-s whose R_{ct} values are tabulated in Table 4. Thus, CdS-c NPs offer lesser resistance to charge transfer at electrode-electrolyte interface, thus promoting facile charge transfer enhancing its PEC performance.

Figure 10: Nyquist Plots in the frequency range 0.01 to 10⁵ Hz for CdS Nanoparticles prepared using different methods.

4.2 Cyclic Voltammetry (CV)

Figure 11 represents the CV curves for different CdS NPs deposited on Ni foam. The CV scans are performed in the potential window ranging from -0.5 to 0.5 V (vs Ag/AgCl) at a scan rate of 10 mV/s which then converted to Standard Hydrogen Electrode (SHE) values as shown in figures 11(A-C). The relation used for this conversion is,

$$E \text{ (vs NHE)} = E \text{ (vs Ag/AgCl)} + 0.197 + 0.059 * pH$$

where pH of 1M KOH solution is 14.

The oxidation and reduction peaks in CV curves illustrate the redox active behavior of all CdS NPs. The solid curves are for dark measurements and dotted curves correspond to light measurements (figures (A)-(C)). From CV curves in (A), we can observe a rapid and significant increase in the photocurrent density i.e. from 1.03 to 1.57 mA/cm² (Haram et al. 2001). The prominent peaks of oxidation and reduction in CdS-c attributes to its higher charge transfer capability as observed from EIS results also. Further, we observed smallest reduction potential (E_{red}) for CdS-c NPs which are tabulated in Table 4. This small potential further signifies the lower onset potential for HER in case of CdS-c NPs. Thus, it is a clear evidence of higher photo electrochemical activity of CdS-c NPs as compared to other two.

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Figure 11: CV curves at scan rate of 10 mV/s for CdS NPs prepared using different methods in dark (solid curve) and under illumination (dotted curve).

Table 4: Charge Transfer Resistance (R_{ct} (Ω)), Reduction Potential (E_{red} . (V)) and photocurrent density (mA/cm^2) for CdS NPs.

Sample	R_{ct} (Ω)	E_{red} . (V)	Current Density(mA/cm^2) (Dark)	Current Density(mA/cm^2) (light)
CdS-c	13	0.74	1.03	1.57
CdS-h	32	0.84	0.64	0.79
CdS-s	37	0.85	1.09	1.27

5. Conclusions

From this experimental study, we established that CdS nanoparticles synthesized by different methods exhibit different structural, morphological and optical properties. The size of synthesized nanoparticles calculated from TEM came out to be in good agreement with the crystallite size determined from XRD. The decrease in energy gap for CdS-c and CdS-h NPs signifies the formation of trap states and creation of defects in the crystal structure which is justified from the increased strain and dislocation density evaluated from XRD. The quenching in intensity of emission peak in PL spectra of CdS-c and CdS-h NPs further confirms the presence of trap/metastable states and efficient charge separation, which is favorable for enhancing photocatalytic activity. The potential electrocatalytic activity of CdS-c NPs can be inferred from the significant reduction in charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) from 37 Ω (for CdS-s) to 13 Ω . From the CV measurements, we demonstrated that CdS-c NPs deposited electrode

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exhibits highest photocurrent density and lower reduction potential among the synthesized samples. All these results confirm that synthesis procedures have direct influence on the photo as well as electrocatalytic activity of catalysts. This is due to the change in characteristic properties of material like its crystallinity, crystal structure, defects, morphology etc. Thus, we conclude that overall photoelectrochemical performance of a material can be enhanced by reducing the size of nanoparticles for increasing the surface-active sites. Also, creation of defects in the crystal structure helps in efficient charge separation which is beneficial for improving the PEC performance of material as observed in case of CdS-c NPs.

6. References

Abdullahi, S. S., Güner, S., Musa, Y. K. I. M., Adamu, B. I., & Abdulhamid, M. I. (2016). Simple method for the determination of band gap of a nanopowdered sample using Kubelka Munk theory. *Journal of the Nigerian Association of Mathematical Physics*, 35, 241-246.

Bindu, P., & Thomas, S. (2014). Estimation of lattice strain in ZnO nanoparticles: X-ray peak profile analysis. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Physics*, 8, 123-134.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40094-014-0141-9>

Bykkam, S., Ahmadipour, M., Narisngam, S., Kalagadda, V. R., & Chidurala, S. C. (2015). Extensive studies on X-ray diffraction of green synthesized silver nanoparticles. *Adv. Nanopart*, 4(1), 1-10. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/anp.2015.41001>

Gupta, T., & Chauhan, R. P. (2021). Structural, morphological, and electrical properties of ZnSe nanostructures: Effects of Zn precursors. *Surfaces and Interfaces*, 25, 101196.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2021.101196>

Hamdani, I. R., & Bhaskarwar, A. N. (2021). Recent progress in material selection and device designs for photoelectrochemical water-splitting. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 138, 110503. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110503>

Haram, S. K., Quinn, B. M., & Bard, A. J. (2001). Electrochemistry of CdS nanoparticles: a correlation between optical and electrochemical band gaps. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 123(36), 8860-8861. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja0158206>

He, R., Qian, X. F., Yin, J., Xi, H. A., Bian, L. J., & Zhu, Z. K. (2003). Formation of monodispersed PVP-capped ZnS and CdS nanocrystals under microwave irradiation. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 220(1-3), 151-157. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-7757\(03\)00072-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-7757(03)00072-4)

Hisatomi, T., Kubota, J., & Domen, K. (2014). Recent advances in semiconductors for photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical water splitting. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 43(22), 7520-7535. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3CS60378D>

Holder, C. F., & Schaak, R. E. (2019). Tutorial on powder X-ray diffraction for characterizing nanoscale materials. *Acs Nano*, 13(7), 7359-7365. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.9b05157>

Huang, Q., Ye, Z., & Xiao, X. (2015). Recent progress in photocathodes for hydrogen evolution. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, 3(31), 15824-15837. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5TA03594E>

Hullavarad, N.V., Hullavarad, S.S., & Karulkar, P.C. (2008). Cadmium sulphide (CdS) nanotechnology: synthesis and applications. *Journal of nanoscience and nanotechnology*, 8(7), 3272-3299. <https://doi.org/10.1166/jnn.2008.145>

Ke, G. L., Jia, B., He, H. C., Zhou, Y., & Zhou, M. (2022). State-of-the-art advancements of transition metal oxides as photoelectrode materials for solar water splitting. *Rare Metals*, 41(7), 2370-2386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12598-022-01968-5>

Khatter, J., & Chauhan, R. P. (2020). Effect of temperature on properties of cadmium sulfide nanostructures synthesized by solvothermal method. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 31(3), 2676-2685. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-019-02807-7>

Kumar, S., & Ojha, A. K. (2016). In-situ synthesis of reduced graphene oxide decorated with highly dispersed ferromagnetic CdS nanoparticles for enhanced photocatalytic activity under UV

irradiation. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 171, 126-136.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2015.12.008>

Kumar, V., Singh, K., Kumar, A., Kumar, M., Singh, K., Vij, A., & Thakur, A. (2017). Effect of solvent on crystallographic, morphological and optical properties of SnO₂ nanoparticles. *Materials Research Bulletin*, 85, 202-208.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.materresbull.2016.09.020>

Mahendia, P., Chauhan, G., Wadhwa, H., Kandhol, G., Mahendia, S., Srivastava, R., & Kumar, S. (2021). Study of induced structural, optical and electrochemical properties of Poly (3-hexylthiophene)(P3HT),[6, 6]-phenyl-C61-butyric-acid-methyl-ester (PCBM) and their blend as an effect of graphene doping. *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*, 148, 109644.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpics.2020.109644>

Iesalnieks, M., Vanags, M., Alsiņa, L. L., Eglītis, R., Grīnberga, L., Sherrell, P. C., & Šutka, A. (2024). Efficient Decoupled Electrolytic Water Splitting in Acid through Pseudocapacitive TiO₂. *Advanced Science*, 2401261. <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202401261>

Nasir, J. A., ur Rehman, Z., Shah, S. N. A., Khan, A., Butler, I. S., & Catlow, C. R. A. (2020). Recent developments and perspectives in CdS-based photocatalysts for water splitting. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, 8(40), 20752-20780. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TA05834C>

Pedersen, K. (2006). Quantum size effects in nanostructures. *Organic and Inorganic Nanostructures*.

Peng, X. (2003). Mechanisms for the shape-control and shape-evolution of colloidal semiconductor nanocrystals. *Advanced Materials*, 15(5), 459-463.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.200390107>

Rahane, G. K., Jathar, S. B., Rondiya, S. R., Jadhav, Y. A., Barma, S. V., Rokade, A., & Jadkar, S. R. (2021). Photoelectrochemical investigation on the cadmium sulfide (CdS) thin films prepared using spin coating technique. *ES Materials & Manufacturing*, 11, 57-64.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.30919/esmm5f1041>

Rao, B. S., Kumar, B. R., Reddy, V. R., Rao, T. S., & Chalapathi, G. V. (2011). Preparation and characterization of CdS nanoparticles by chemical co-precipitation technique. *Chalcogenide Lett*, 8(3), 177-185.

Roduner, E. (2006). Size matters: why nanomaterials are different. *Chemical society reviews*, 35(7), 583-592. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B502142C>

Streetman, B. G., & Banerjee, S. (2006). *Solid state electronic devices* (Vol. 10). Upper Saddle River: Pearson/Prentice Hall.

Tang, H., Yan, M., Zhang, H., Xia, M., & Yang, D. (2005). Preparation and characterization of water-soluble CdS nanocrystals by surface modification of ethylene diamine. *Materials letters*, 59(8-9), 1024-1027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2004.11.049>

Thakur, A., Ghosh, D., Devi, P., Kim, K. H., & Kumar, P. (2020). Current progress and challenges in photoelectrode materials for the production of hydrogen. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 397, 125415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.125415>

Thambidurai, M., Muthukumarasamy, N., Agilan, S., Murugan, N., Vasantha, S., Balasundaraprabhu, R., & Senthil, T. S. (2010). Strong quantum confinement effect in nanocrystalline CdS. *Journal of materials science*, 45(12), 3254-3258. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-010-4333-7>

Tripathi, B., Singh, F., Avasthi, D. K., Bhati, A. K., Das, D., & Vijay, Y. K. (2008). Structural, optical, electrical and positron annihilation studies of CdS: Fe system. *Journal of alloys and compounds*, 454(1-2), 97-101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2007.01.016>

Wang, Q., Lian, J., Li, J., Wang, R., Huang, H., Su, B., & Lei, Z. (2015). Highly efficient photocatalytic hydrogen production of flower-like cadmium sulfide decorated by histidine. *Scientific reports*, 5(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep13593>

Xu, P., Liu, J., Yan, P., Miao, C., Ye, K., Cheng, K., & Wang, G. (2016). Preparation of porous cadmium sulphide on nickel foam: a novel electrode material with excellent supercapacitor

performance. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, 4(13), 4920-4928.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C5TA09740A>

Yasin, G., Ibraheem, S., Ali, S., Arif, M., Ibrahim, S., Iqbal, R., & Zhao, W. (2022). Defects-engineered tailoring of tri-doped interlinked metal-free bifunctional catalyst with lower gibbs free energy of OER/HER intermediates for overall water splitting. *Materials Today Chemistry*, 23, 100634. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtchem.2021.100634>

Zhu, L., Feng, C., Li, F., Zhang, D., Li, C., Wang, Y., & Chen, Z. (2014). Excellent gas sensing and optical properties of single-crystalline cadmium sulfide nanowires. *RSC advances*, 4(106), 61691-61697. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4RA11010B>